

FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AMONG COMPACT SUVs CAR OWNERS: A CASE STUDY ON AN AUTOMOTIVE COMPANY IN MALAYSIA

Hanifah Binti Maksin^{1*}, Mohamd Irwan Bin Khalil², Shahrizal Bin Md Zainal³,
Low Chee Him⁴, Yap Den Hau⁵, Musalizam Bin Musa⁶

^{1,2,3,4,5,6} Faculty of Business, UNITAR International University, Malaysia

*Corresponding author, hanifahm@unitar.my

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to examine the relationship between comfort, cabin space, design, social life, value for money, and customer satisfaction among compact SUV car owners at a Malaysian automaker. The study involved 407 samples of compact SUV car owners who responded to a questionnaire with their opinions. The findings revealed that comfort, cabin space, and value for money were significant factors in determining customer satisfaction among owners of compact SUVs. Despite the subjectivity of design, this factor did not significantly influence the overall customer satisfaction of compact SUV car owners. Similarly, social life factors, such as the social status associated with owning a particular car brand or model, were discovered to have no significant impact on customer satisfaction. The study highlights the need for this automaker to prioritize comfort, cabin space, and value when designing and marketing compact SUVs to increase customer satisfaction. Future research will examine strategies to optimize the comfort, cabin space, and value for money aspects to meet customer expectations and increase their overall satisfaction.

Keywords: comfort, cabin space, value for money, customer satisfaction, automotive

INTRODUCTION

Customer satisfaction is frequently impacted by the interactions consumers have with different businesses (Nunkoo et al., 2020). The relationship between perceived quality and customer satisfaction during different service phases is contingent upon the nature of the services provided, as posited by Cho et al. (2021). According to Dalla Pozza et al. (2018), it is necessary to assess customer satisfaction throughout the entire service process, encompassing the initial expectation phase to the post-experience evaluation stage.

The impact of post-experience on customer satisfaction is significant, as it influences clients' perception of the services provided. According to Birch-Jensen et al. (2021), it is imperative for companies to evaluate and modify the standard of service provided to their clients to ensure the sustenance of enduring client relationships. The relationship between the quality dimensions of after-sale service and customer satisfaction has been investigated in various industries such as banking services (Nunkoo et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2019), telecommunication

(Abd-Elrahman & Ahmed Kamal, 2020), insurance (Dalla Pozza et al., 2018), and automotive (Jain et al., 2020; James et al., 2021). Extensive research has been conducted on consumer satisfaction in the automotive industry (Asian et al., 2019; Balinado et al., 2021; Nassiri Pirbazari & Jalilian, 2020; Waluya et al., 2019; Zygiaris et al., 2022), focusing on various aspects of the customer experience. Waluya et al. (2019) have analyzed the effect of product quality and brand image on consumer satisfaction, examining variables such as durability, performance, and safety features. The service experience, which includes vehicle maintenance, repairs, and after-sales support (Balinado et al., 2021; Moxsin et al., 2023; Zygiaris et al., 2022) has also been investigated, with a particular emphasis on service responsiveness. The incorporation of technology and innovation into vehicles, such as advanced infotainment systems and driver-assistance technologies (Asian et al., 2019) has also been investigated. In addition, environmental factors and cultural/geographic variations have been analyzed to better comprehend their impact on consumer satisfaction (Mattioli et al., 2020).

In Malaysia, as reported by Paul Tan Automotive News, the sales of sport utility vehicles (SUVs) are skyrocketing by 43% in the year 2021 (Chan, 2022). According to Malaysia Automotive Association in 2019, SUVs accounted for almost 25% of the total number of private vehicles (Asyraf, 2023). The figure is alarming the automotive company to examine what factors that influence the satisfaction of the SUVs car owners. This study is being held on an automotive company in Malaysia to understand customer satisfaction by developing a strategic plan and improving the process efficiency to meet and satisfy customer expectations. With the compact SUVs market rapidly expanding and more car manufacturers begin to switch their focus from producing sedan cars to SUVs and compact SUVs car, it is critical for management to gain a better understanding of what consumers are concerned about. Management should realize that consumers' taste is different from year to year. Thus, useful knowledge of understanding target customers can give this company a competitive advantage in competing with competitors within the same industry. Where at the same time, it also would help marketing more options to analyze based on data collection from this study. Marketing would be able to identify what are the customer's actual needs so that a projection and channel directly to management based on feedback given by the customer to expand and improve the product lineup of compact SUVs cars.

This study sought to answer if there is a significant relationship between comfort, cabin space, design, social life, value for money and customer satisfaction among compact SUVs car owners.

LITERATURE REVIEW

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Customer satisfaction is crucial to long-term success for companies (Kotler, 2018). Consumer's opinion of the service quality offered by the automotive service centers in terms of technical excellence and customer service was what affected the brand image and customer loyalty. Thus, this is very important since loyalty can attract new customers and retain current customers (Subaebasni et al., 2019).

Relationship between comfort and customer satisfaction

The automotive company conducted a study on car seat attributes as a means of obtaining a better understanding of customers' comfort perceptions, as reported by Bastian et al. (2021). Besides car seats, interior comfort (Wang & Chen, 2020) is also attributed to customer

satisfaction when purchasing a car. Driving comforts (Joshi & Bhatt, 2018) have also been found to customers prioritize and are significant considerations to customer satisfaction. Hence, this study highlights the relationship between comfort and customer satisfaction.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between comfort and customer satisfaction amongst compact SUVs car owners.

Relationship between cabin space and customer satisfaction

Adequate space ensures passengers comfort and satisfaction (Litman, 2017), this factor is examined because of travelling distance and driving. Cabin space also refers to the interior temperature of a vehicle, emphasizing the importance of maintaining an optimal temperature for a pleasant travel experience (Mohiuddin et al., 2019). According to Dzunova et al. (2021) cabin space also includes the vehicle impacts on air ventilation. Vehicle room space, interior temperature control and air ventilation point the need in the automotive industry to enhance customer satisfaction. Thus, this study would like to examine the relationship between cabin space and customer satisfaction.

H₂: There is a significant relationship between cabin space and customer satisfaction amongst compact SUVs car owners.

Relationship between design and customer satisfaction

Car design traits and pictures of car styles can help car makers make cars that keep up with the latest technological advances (Syahidi et al., 2020). The car design being a great concern to the decision on purchasing a car whether design meets customer standards (Kowang et al., 2018). This study would like to know the relationship between design and customer satisfaction.

H₃: There is a significant relationship between design and customer satisfaction amongst compact SUVs car owners.

Relationship between social life and customer satisfaction

Automobile ownership and use can be viewed as an essential need for social inclusion in developed countries, they rely significantly on extensive automotive access. However, motorized transportation utilization and emissions remain relatively low in developing countries. Mattioli et al. (2020) examine the social, political, and economic issues that influence automobile manufacturers' decisions. Hence, this study highlights the relationship between social life and customer satisfaction.

H₄: There is a significant relationship between social life and customer satisfaction amongst compact SUVs car owners.

Relationship between value for money and customer satisfaction

Customer value for money can be defined as the advantages received less the costs incurred. The value includes not only the cost of the car paid for by the consumer, but also non-monetary variables such as time, effort, energy, and inconvenience. According to Mahajan (2020), these additional costs can include expenses for petrol, taxes, spare components, and car servicing. Customer satisfaction has been demonstrated to be highly influenced by the relationship between perceived pricing and service quality (Witama & Keni, 2020). Automotive firms recognize the importance of value for money by investing in developing a positive brand image and exhibiting car technology to increase customer satisfaction (Mokhtar & Shamsudin, 2020). The importance of consumer perception and satisfaction in the automobile sector is highlighted by the emphasis on value for money. As well, this study this study would like to examine the relationship between value for money and customer satisfaction.

H₅: There is a significant relationship between value for money and customer satisfaction amongst compact SUVs car owners.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 illustrates the theoretical framework used in this study. The dependent variable is customer satisfaction. This study is trying to determine if five independent variables; comfort, cabin space, design, social life, value for money have a significant relationship with customer satisfaction.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework of the Research

METHODS

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study used the quantitative method that will help the researchers to gain information and insight into the relationship among the variables and their level of significance. This study collected primary data using an online questionnaire that was distributed to compact SUVs

cars' owner of an automotive company in Malaysia. Likert scales were used to measure the responses from the participants.

POPULATION AND SAMPLING

The population of this study is derived from the database from this automotive company. Between January 2021 and April 2022, a total of 14,800 owners of compact SUVs were identified.

The present investigation employed convenience sampling as a non-probability sampling method. The provided information lacks a foundation for computing the probability of each element in the population to be included in the sample. This approach would be employed by researchers to select individuals encountered in this study. This suggests that the survey should be distributed to individuals who are readily reachable and present at the designated sampling location. To gather requisite data, respondents are provided with questionnaires in a random manner (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

SAMPLING SIZE

A table that offers a representative sample of a population was developed by Krejcie and Morgan (1970), as noted by Sekaran & Bougie (2016). As per the tabulated data, the statistical assessment of population (N) comprising 14,800 individuals necessitates a sample (S) of 370 responses. This research successfully collected 407 survey responses.

QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

The questionnaire consists of two sections. The questionnaire begins with Section A that contains six subsections. This section used the five-point Likert interval scale, where 1 is assigned to 'Strongly Disagree', and 5 to 'Strongly Agree', which is consistent with extensively utilized scales (Zikmund et al., 2013). The questions were based on the factors mentioned in the research's independent variables on comfort, cabin space, design, social life, value for money and dependent variable of customer satisfaction. The items are adopted and adapted from previous studies.

Section B is centered on the demographic profile of the participant. Section B of the questionnaire includes inquiries about participant's age, gender, monthly income, level of education, occupation, and marital status.

RESULTS

DEMOGRAPHICS ANALYSIS

Of the total of 407 responses, 52.6% age between 30 – 39 years old. Male respondents are higher than female, where 59.2% are male and 40.8% are females. A significant proportion of the participants (52.6%) reported an income level falling within the range of RM7,5001 and above.

The data indicates that a significant proportion of the respondents possess postgraduate qualifications (51.8%), while a slightly smaller proportion hold undergraduate degrees (43.2%). A large percentage of respondents (59.0%) were employed in the private sector, while 55.8% of them reported being married with children.

DATA ANALYSIS

In this study, the researchers used XLSTAT 2019 to analyze the data.

Table 1. Reliability Test

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Comfort	0.748
Cabin space	0.811
Design	0.830
Social life	0.762
Value for money	0.856
Customer satisfaction	0.795

To assess the reliability of the measurement, this study report Cronbach's α in Table 1. It showed Cronbach's α for Comfort (0.748), Cabin space (0.811), Design (0.830), Social life (0.762), Value for money (0.856) and Customer satisfaction (0.795) confirming consistency reliability as commonly cited minimum threshold of 0.7 for each construct (Hair et al., 2017).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics (Quantitative data)

Statistic Parameter	Comfort (AVR)	Cabin (AVR)	Social (AVR)	Design (AVR)	Value (AVR)	CS (AVR)
Nbr. of observations	407	407	407	407	407	407
Minimum	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Maximum	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000
Median	3.500	3.500	3.500	3.500	3.500	3.500
Sum	1386.250	1376.750	1376.500	1402.250	1396.000	1351.500
Mean	3.406	3.383	3.382	3.445	3.430	3.321
Variance (n-1)	0.222	0.270	0.236	0.277	0.292	0.244
Standard deviation (n-1)	0.471	0.519	0.486	0.526	0.541	0.494
Skewness (Pearson)	-1.445	-1.314	-1.054	-1.124	-1.081	-1.317
Kurtosis (Pearson)	3.507	1.955	1.251	1.086	0.860	2.519

As shown in Table 2, if the scale range is between 1 and 5, with 1 representing "strongly disagree" and 5 representing "strongly agree," the interpretation of mean values are as follows:

The average rating for Comfort is 3.406. This indicates that respondents, on average, rated the level of comfort as slightly above neutral or slightly leaning towards agreement.

The average rating for cabin space is 3.383. This indicates that respondents, on average, rated the cabin space quality as slightly above neutral or slightly leaning towards agreement.

The average rating for social life is 3.382. This indicates that, on average, respondents rated the social aspects (such as amenities and interaction opportunities) as slightly above neutral or leaning slightly towards agreement.

The average rating for Design is 3.445. This indicates that, on average, respondents rated the design aspects (perhaps referring to the overall aesthetic or visual appeal) as slightly above neutral or leaning slightly towards agreement.

The average rating for Value for money is 3.430. This suggests that, on average, respondents viewed the product or service's value (in terms of cost-effectiveness or worthiness) as slightly above neutral or slightly leaning towards agreement.

Finally, Customer satisfaction rating average is 3.321. This indicates that, on average, respondents rated their satisfaction with the product or service as slightly above neutral or slightly leaning towards agreement.

Based on the criteria provided by George & Mallery (2010), Hair et al. (2010), and Bryne (2010), which consider skewness between -2 and +2 as acceptable and kurtosis between -7 and +7 as indicative of a normal univariate distribution, The normality of the variables can be interpreted in the following manner:

Skewness interpretation:

All variables have skewness values falling within the acceptable range of -2 to +2. This suggests that, based on this criterion, the distributions of the variables can be considered reasonably close to a normal distribution.

Kurtosis interpretation:

The kurtosis values provided in the descriptive statistics were all below +3.507 (the upper limit mentioned in the previous response). However, based on the criteria mentioned by Hair et al. (2010) and Bryne (2010), which allow kurtosis between -7 and +7, the kurtosis values for all variables still fall within an acceptable range.

Overall, according to the criteria mentioned by George & Mallery (2010), Hair et al. (2010), and Bryne (2010), the skewness and kurtosis values of the variables suggest that the data is reasonably close to a normal univariate distribution.

LINEAR REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Table 3. Multicollinearity Statistics

	Comfort(AVR)	Cabin(AVR)	Social (AVR)	Design(AVR)	Value(AVR)
Tolerance	0.335	0.269	0.219	0.223	0.216
VIF	2.984	3.715	4.564	4.486	4.632

The general guideline for determining the presence of multicollinearity using the variance inflation factor (VIF) as displayed in Table 3 is as follows:

VIF values below 1: There is no multicollinearity.

VIF values between 1 and 5: There is low to moderate multicollinearity, which is generally considered acceptable.

VIF values above 5: There is a high degree of multicollinearity, indicating that the variables are highly correlated and may pose challenges in the regression analysis.

It's important to note that the specific threshold for determining multicollinearity may vary depending on the context and the field of study. Some researchers may consider a higher threshold, such as 10, to define significant multicollinearity.

In this data, the VIF values range from 2.984 to 4.632, which suggests the presence of multicollinearity. While the VIF values are below the commonly used threshold of 5, they are relatively high, indicating a moderate level of multicollinearity.

Table 4. Goodness of fit statistics

Items	Result
Observations	407.000
Sum of weights	407.000
DF	401.000
R ²	0.682
Adjusted R ²	0.678

R-squared or coefficient of determination is a goodness-of-fit a statistical in a regression model that determines the proportion of variance in the dependent variable which is customer satisfaction that can be explained by the independent variable which are comfort, cabin space, design, social life, and value for money. As found in Table 4, the R² value, 0.682, represents the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variables in the regression model. It indicates that approximately 68.2% of the variability in the dependent variable is accounted for by the independent variables included in the model.

In this study the adjusted R² value, 0.678, is a modified version of R² that adjusts for the number of predictors in the model and the degrees of freedom. It penalizes the inclusion of unnecessary variables. In this case, the adjusted R² is slightly lower than the R², indicating that the model's predictive power is slightly reduced when accounting for the number of predictors and degrees of freedom.

Table 5. Analysis of variance

Source	DF	Sum of squares	Mean squares	F	Pr > F
Model	5	67.566	13.513	172.216	< 0.0001
Error	401	31.465	0.078		
Corrected Total	406	99.032			

Computed against model Y=Mean(Y)

According to Table 5, the model has 5 degrees of freedom (DF) and explains a significant amount of variance in the dependent variable. The F-statistic is 172.216, and the p-value (Pr > F) is less than 0.0001, indicating that the model is highly significant in explaining the variation in customer satisfaction.

Table 6. Regression coefficients result

Source	Value	Standard error	t	Pr > t	Lower bound (99%)	Upper bound (99%)
Intercept	0.296	0.106	2.779	0.006	0.020	0.571
Comfort(AVR)	0.331	0.051	6.506	< 0.0001	0.200	0.463
Cabin(AVR)	0.254	0.052	4.923	< 0.0001	0.120	0.388
Social(AVR)	0.053	0.061	0.872	0.384	-0.105	0.211
Design(AVR)	0.079	0.056	1.413	0.159	-0.066	0.224
Value(AVR)	0.170	0.055	3.077	0.002	0.027	0.314

Comfort, Cabin space, and Value for money have highly significant p-values (< 0.0001), as shown in Table 6, indicating that they are strongly associated with Customer satisfaction. However, Social life and Design have p-values above the conventional threshold of 0.05, suggesting that their associations with Customer satisfaction may not be statistically significant.

These findings suggest that Comfort, Cabin space, and Value for money are important predictors in explaining the variance in Customer satisfaction. However, the significance of social life and Design may be questionable.

Table 7. Standardized Coefficients

Source	Value	Standard error	t	Pr > t	Lower bound (99%)	Upper bound (99%)
Comfort(AVR)	0.316	0.049	6.506	< 0.0001	0.191	0.442
Cabin(AVR)	0.267	0.054	4.923	< 0.0001	0.127	0.407
Social (AVR)	0.052	0.060	0.872	0.384	-0.103	0.208
Design(AVR)	0.084	0.060	1.413	0.159	-0.070	0.239
Value(AVR)	0.186	0.061	3.077	0.002	0.030	0.343

The standardized coefficients in Table 7 provide information about the relative importance and impact of each predictor variable on the dependent variable. These coefficients represent the effect of each predictor when they are standardized, allowing for a comparison of their relative contributions (Siegel & Wagner, 2022)

The standardized coefficient for Comfort is 0.316, indicating that a one-standard-deviation increase in Comfort is associated with a 0.316 standard deviation increase in Customer satisfaction. It has a significant p-value (< 0.0001), suggesting that Comfort has a strong positive impact on Customer satisfaction.

The standardized coefficient for Cabin space is 0.267, indicating that a one-standard-deviation increase in Cabin space is associated with a 0.267 standard deviation increase in Customer satisfaction. It also has a significant p-value (< 0.0001), indicating a strong positive impact on Customer satisfaction.

The standardized coefficient for Social life is 0.052, suggesting that a one-standard-deviation increase in Social life corresponds to a 0.052 standard deviation increase in Customer satisfaction. However, the p-value (0.384) is not significant at the conventional threshold ($p > 0.05$), indicating that the impact of Social life on Customer satisfaction may not be statistically significant.

The standardized coefficient for Design is 0.084, indicating that a one-standard-deviation increase in Design corresponds to a 0.084 standard deviation increase in Customer satisfaction. However, the p-value (0.159) suggests that the impact of Design on Customer satisfaction may not be statistically significant.

The standardized coefficient for Value for Money is 0.186, indicating that a one-standard-deviation increase in Value for money is associated with a 0.186 standard deviation increase in Customer satisfaction. It has a significant p-value (0.002), suggesting a strong positive impact on Customer satisfaction.

It's important to consider both the magnitude of the standardized coefficients and their associated p-values when assessing the relative importance and significance of each predictor. In this case, Comfort, Cabin space, and Value for money appear to be the most influential predictors in explaining Customer satisfaction. Social life and Design may have less statistically significant contributions.

SUMMARY OF HYPHOTHESES

To determine whether the hypothesis is being accepted or rejected, p-value from table 7 above will be referred. The summary of the hypotheses results is shown in Table 8 below:

Table 8 - Hypothesis results

	HYPOTHESIS DESCRIPTION	P-Value	RESULT
H ₁	There is a relationship between comfort and customer satisfaction among compact SUVs car owners	< 0.0001	ACCEPTED
H ₂	There is a relationship between cabin space and customer satisfaction among compact SUVs car owners	< 0.0001	ACCEPTED
H ₃	There is a relationship between design and customer satisfaction among compact SUVs car owners	0.384	REJECTED
H ₄	There is a relationship between social life and customer satisfaction among compact SUVs car owners	0.159	REJECTED
H ₅	There is a relationship between value for money and customer satisfaction among compact SUVs car owners	0.002	ACCEPTED

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

The standardized coefficient for comfort is 0.316. this is the highest standard coefficient indicating that this factor is the main factor for the compact SUVs car owner's satisfaction. The SUVs offer capacious interiors, ample legroom, and a more comfortable ride because of their higher ground clearance and advanced suspension. Additionally, SUVs frequently include comfort-enhancing features such as adjustable seating, climate control, and advanced infotainment systems. The perception of safety, versatility, and practicality add to the appeal of SUVs as comfortable vehicles. The results mentioned above are significantly influenced by the fact that 60% of the respondents are car owners who are married and have children. Individuals with familial responsibilities tend to emphasize comfort to a significant extent when making their choices. The result might be different if respondents comprise more of car owners who are single.

For cabin space, the relationship is significant. Cabin space is the second highest factor after comfort (standardized coefficient 0.267). Cabin space as refers to the room space, interior temperature, and air ventilation of a vehicle, incorporate for a pleasant travel experience. (Mohiuddin et al., 2019; Dzunova et al., 2021) as again most respondents were car owners who are married and have children, this factor determines their satisfaction in having SUVs car.

There is no association between design and customer satisfaction. This finding did not match with previous studies that design has a significant influence on customer satisfaction in owning a car (Nassiri Pirbazari & Jalilian, 2020; Kowang et al., 2018). This result can be explained by looking at compact SUVs design is subjective, and individual tastes vary greatly. The respondents of this study may find visually alluring may not appeal to another. Moreover, performance, dependability, safety features, and interior comfort are frequently prioritized by customers over aesthetics. These functional factors have a more direct and tangible effect on satisfaction. Furthermore, car design trends evolve over time, and as patterns change, the

initial impact of design may diminish. Despite the design's potential indirect influence on brand image and initial impressions, its direct effect on long-term customer satisfaction may be less significant.

This study reports that there are no relationships between social life and customer satisfaction of compact SUVs car owners. The results supported the conclusion of a previous study that social life has no effect on consumer satisfaction (Mattioli et al., 2020). As a developing country, Malaysia still does not associate social life with the pleasure of car ownership. There are various reasons why social life may not have a substantial association with customer satisfaction in a developing country. Economic factors take precedence, as price and basic transit requirements are frequently prioritised over social features. Customers in Malaysia might be more concerned with pricing, dependability, and functionality than with social prestige or connections. Customers are more inclined to choose a car's performance, and value for money over its social image.

Finally for independent variable of value for money is proven to have a significant relationship with customer satisfaction among compact SUVs car owners. In line with similar studies, customers perceive an automobile to be good value for money when it strikes a balance between its price and the benefits it gives. This perspective has a role in their overall satisfaction with the purchase. Customers also have specific expectations about the features, performance, and quality they expect from an automobile depending on its pricing. For this study, the compact SUVs car owners entails continuing costs, and when a vehicle provides good value for money, it is considered as cost-effective to purchase and operate over its lifetime. Customers expect a certain degree of quality, dependability, safety features, and technology for their money, and when a car meets these expectations at an affordable price, customer satisfaction increases.

This study has added to the literature on understanding factors that influence the customer satisfaction among compact SUVs car owners in one of an automotive company in Malaysia. However, the result of this study cannot be generalized since the respondents only come from the database in one single company. It is good if in the future the comparison being made to more different automotive company so the result might be more accurate and representing car owners' satisfaction on having compact SUVs cars.

Future research on consumer satisfaction in the automobile industry will most likely concentrate on a variety of topics. These include investigating the impact of electric and autonomous vehicles on satisfaction, investigating personalization and customization options, investigating the role of connectivity and infotainment systems, investigating the impact of sustainable features, researching digital and online channels for car purchasing, and comprehending the significance of post-purchase services and experiences. Researchers will continue to dive into these areas as technology, customer preferences, and sustainability concerns advance to fulfil the changing demands and expectations of car buyers.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection and analysis and writing and revising the manuscript.

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